

Research and Applications

Attitudes about public outreach among NASA scientists and engineers

Chris Mead¹, Sanlyn Buxner², Heather Fischer³, Colleen Manning⁴, MaryKay Severino⁵, Andy Shaner⁶, Martin Storksdieck³, Jessica L. Swann¹, Patricia Udomprasert⁷

¹School of Earth and Science Exploration, Arizona State University, ²Planetary Science Institute, ³STEM Research Center, Oregon State University, ⁴Goodman Research Group, Inc., ⁵ARISA Lab, ⁶Universities Space Research Association, ⁷Center for Astrophysics, Harvard & Smithsonian

Many scientists engage in public outreach and engagement activities. Outreach is a particularly present concern for scientists and engineers who work directly or indirectly with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), as the agency funds numerous outreach programmes. For these programmes to work effectively with the many scientists and engineers interested in contributing to outreach efforts, it is important to understand what motivates these professionals to engage in outreach, the challenges they face in doing this work, and the training they would benefit from. In this article, we report the results of a survey on these topics, which received responses from more than 200 scientists and engineers with expertise related to NASA science. Where possible, we also compare our findings from this population to prior studies of attitudes toward outreach among scientists from other disciplines. We hope these results will inform practices among organisations both within and outside NASA, leading to more effective partnerships between experts in outreach and education, and science and engineering professionals.

Edited by

Fatemeh Bonyadi

Reviewed by

Astronomy Education Journal

Submitted 15 January 2025

Accepted 24 June 2025

Published 1 August 2025

Corresponding Author

Chris Mead

chris.mead@asu.edu

Citation

Mead, C., Buxner, S., Fischer, H., Manning, C., Severino, M., Shaner, A., Storksdieck, M., Swann, J. L., & Udomprasert, P. (2025).

Attitudes about public outreach among NASA scientists and engineers.

Communicating Astronomy with the Public Journal, 19(2).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16939220>

1. Introduction

1.1. Institutional Background NASA policy documents make it clear that public communication of science is a key part of the organisation's mission ([NASA Strategic Plan, n.d., Strategic Objective 4.3](#)). Moreover, NASA's science experts are explicitly identified as contributing to the achievement of these objectives. It is also clear that this mission has been understood and taken up by working scientists with connections to NASA. NASA mission priorities are substantially shaped by the Decadal Surveys ([Most Recent Decadal Surveys - NASA Science, n.d.](#)) that are written by leaders in each of the five scientific divisions within NASA (i.e. Biological and Physical Sciences, Earth Science, Planetary Science and Astrobiology, Astrophysics, and Heliophysics). Although the vast majority of space in these documents is dedicated to scientific questions and missions that might address those questions, in all cases, attention has also been paid to the role that the discipline

plays in public communication of science towards the goal of inspiring the next generation of scientists or raising public awareness of NASA science ([National Academies of Sciences, 2018](#), p. 407; [2023a](#), p. 434; [2023b](#), p. 535; [2023c](#), pp. 220–221, 228–229; [National Research Council, 2013](#), pp. 92–93).

Against this backdrop, the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) established the Science Activation programme (SciAct; [Learn–NASA Science, n.d.](#)) with the goal of funding teams with expertise in science outreach and education to help bring NASA science and scientists to the public, thereby achieving its strategic goals. After five years, this programme was comprehensively reviewed by the National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine ([National Academies of Science, 2019](#)). Although the report commended many of SciAct’s successes, it also highlighted some areas of weakness. One of the problems identified was the need for stronger and more effective connections with NASA’s scientists, engineers, and mission personnel. Engaging NASA scientists in meaningful and productive ways, though, required learning more about their interests, needs, backgrounds and motivations, which provided the impetus for the present study, whose results we report on here.

1.2. Who we are and why we did this work The authors are a group of Earth and space science educators, outreach specialists, programme evaluators, and education researchers who work on projects as part of the NASA SciAct portfolio. The present work originated as an assessment of each project to understand how to engage with “subject matter experts” (SMEs) to better meet their needs in the area of outreach and public engagement. The results from this work have already informed the work that each of us has engaged in, and we hope to share these results more broadly with the astronomy education and outreach community.

1.3. Research Context Understanding how scientists feel about public outreach is not a new area of inquiry. To properly situate our work in the broader context, we summarise other work that has also addressed this topic, both in space science and in science more broadly.

A recent edited volume on astronomy education and outreach provides a thorough argument for the unique power that astronomy has to intrigue and excite the public ([Kaminski, 2021](#)). Authors include both professional astronomers and those who work with students and the public, highlighting the breadth of opportunities to engage with the public through outreach and more in-depth engagement. Outstanding imagery, opportunities to analyse data, and ways to engage students and the public in meaningful projects summarise why there is so much interest in understanding our Universe through engaging in astronomy. [Dang and Russo \(2015\)](#) surveyed IAU members and found that many supported dedicating a larger percentage of research to outreach activities.

Similar points have been argued in many other disciplines. As [Bowring \(2013\)](#) explains from his perspective as a geochronologist, the general (US) public has a very poor grasp of the age of the Earth and Deep Time. This, in turn, exacerbates efforts by scientists to help explain the

evidence for climate change, as well as the process of evolution in other areas of science. Scientific outreach, with its evocative examples of dinosaurs and other extinct life forms, should be one way that scientists collectively work to address the public's understanding of science. Beyond geology, similar calls have also come from ecology (e.g., [Bush et al., 2018](#)), biology (e.g., [Varner, 2014](#)), genetics (e.g., [Scheufele et al., 2021](#)), and chemistry (e.g., [Mackay et al., 2020](#)), each highlighting the distinctive reasons why those disciplines can both excite and inform the public.

Beyond these calls from specific disciplinary scientists, the value and need for outreach have also been taken up by groups such as the American Association for the Advancement of Science ([AAAS, 2016](#)). The AAAS developed a Theory of Change for these activities. In addition to the visibility that the AAAS brings, this effort establishes a logic model that is notable for emphasizing outcomes for the scientists engaging in outreach.

Multiple sources indicate that a significant portion of scientists in the US are involved in some form of outreach or public communication activities (e.g., [Johnson et al., 2014](#); [Rose et al., 2020](#)). Similarly, surveys of astronomers both in the US and internationally show that they engage in outreach activities, whether through lectures, classroom engagements, or other interactions with the general public (e.g., [Dang & Russo, 2015](#)). Studies of scientists who engage in outreach have consistently found that outreach scientists believe their outreach efforts are valuable both for themselves and the audiences they work with. Sources of intrinsic motivation for scientists engaging in outreach include attracting more women to the field, increasing scientific literacy, a desire to contribute, defending science from misinformation, exciting the public about science, improving teaching skills, and having fun ([Andrews et al., 2005](#); [Dang & Russo, 2015](#); [Dudo & Besley, 2016](#); [Barthel, 2020](#)). Studies show that scientists are more likely to engage in outreach if they are already doing it, have positive attitudes towards it, and believe that they possess strong communication skills ([Poliakoff & Webb, 2007](#); [Besley et al., 2020](#)). Finally, barriers to outreach for scientists include disapproval from supervisors or advisors, perceptions that the public is not interested in science, not feeling comfortable doing outreach, and lack of overall time, information about outreach opportunities, recognition and funding ([Andrews et al., 2005](#); [Ecklund et al., 2012](#); [Woitowich et al., 2022](#)).

Studies of the impact of training for scientists on their subsequent outreach activities reveal that the training scientists receive in communication contributes to their willingness to engage in public communication about science. One set of results highlights the importance of training opportunities that both build scientists' self-efficacy for communication and support the development of positive attitudes towards their audiences ([Coppie et al., 2020](#)). Barthel's results show that the training scientists receive influences not only whether they engage in outreach, but also how they do so ([Barthel, 2020](#)). Finally, a study of AAAS members revealed that scientists are more likely to attend communications training if it focuses on helping scientists craft their online messages to be understandable to the public and to boost their credibility as scientists ([Besley et al., 2015](#)). Overall, the literature suggests that scientists will

be more open to attending training that aligns with their values.

[Lewenstein & Baram-Tsabari \(2022\)](#) draw on ideas from learning progressions to identify threshold concepts for science communication learners. Their work offers a detailed list of learning objectives that would be appropriate for 'occasional' ("new or sporadic science communicators"), 'active' ("individuals [who] have science communication as part of their active identity, but have other primary commitments"), or 'professional' ("[individuals who] consider science one of their major professional identities") science communicators (p.293). These objectives provide a starting point for designers of training programmes that are sensitive to the target audience, and their goals and experience in science communication.

A nationwide programme called Portal to the Public (PoP) was created to connect scientists with informal learning organisations ([Selvakumar & Storksdieck, 2013](#)). It also provided a comprehensive training programme. In a research study investigating this programme and its effects on participating scientists, [Stylinkski et al. \(2018\)](#) conclude that it led to sustained positive impact because it included a foundation in learning theory (i.e. refuting the transmissionist model), included opportunities for participants to develop and practice their outreach work, and effectively connected scientists with audiences.

Another example also emphasises the importance of refining scientists' knowledge of modern educational practices. [Illingworth & Roop \(2015\)](#) present two case studies in which scientists worked directly with education professionals who gave feedback on the scientists' initial outreach activity. Although far less comprehensive than what was done through Portal to the Public, this small study suggests that pairing scientists with practicing teachers is an effective way to reduce a "deficit" framing of outreach activities (i.e. where the scientist's role is conceived to be transmitting missing knowledge to the uninformed public) towards an engagement framing in which scientists take their audiences' prior knowledge, interests, and lived experiences into account (e.g., [Storksdieck et al., 2016](#)).

1.4. Guiding Questions This work was guided by the following questions:

- *What are the perceptions of NASA-funded scientists towards outreach?*
- *What are NASA-funded scientists' motivations and goals for engaging in outreach?*
- *What are the considerations for scientists who want to engage in outreach?*
- *How do these compare to scientists who work outside of Earth and Space sciences?*

2. Methods

Participants for the study were recruited as part of an ongoing effort by the NASA Science Mission Directorate to conduct a needs assessment of the community of scientists and engineers (termed "subject matter experts" or SMEs) regarding their thoughts on engaging in outreach and education activities. The survey questions asked how prepared participants felt

about carrying out these activities and what they needed to be better prepared to do so. Data were collected from 246 individuals in 2021 through an online survey.

2.1. Study Population and Survey Administration The survey was administered through Qualtrics and was open from 26 August to 5 October 2021. The survey was distributed through several listservs that reach NASA SMEs, listed below. The survey was additionally sent to all NASA SciAct projects to distribute to appropriate SMEs within their networks.

- *The Universe of Learning list*
- *A subset of the American Geophysical Union membership*
- *The Lunar-L list*
- *The American Astronomical Society Division for Planetary Sciences*

2.2. Survey Design and Inclusion The full survey can be found in Appendix A. The intent was to survey only SMEs working within NASA-related science; therefore, Question 1 of the survey asked respondents whether they considered themselves to be a “scientist or engineer working on NASA-related topics.” This was left to the respondent’s interpretation to be as inclusive as possible of individuals relevant to the study. The survey would end for individuals who did not identify as such. A total of 246 individuals responded in the affirmative and were invited to complete the entire survey. An additional 17 individuals responded “no” to this question and were not invited to complete the rest of the survey. Of the 246 potentially usable responses, 200 respondents completed the survey, although not all questions were mandatory. The remaining 46 survey respondents can be assumed to have lost interest or been distracted from the survey before submitting their responses; however, all answered at least some questions, so our analysis will include all responses from individuals who identified as working in NASA science or engineering. Response counts will be reported by question in our analyses; variation in these response counts stems from individuals skipping one or more questions. We characterised the members of the community who responded to the survey using demographic questions at the end of the survey and their response to Q1.

Because we do not have direct access to the email addresses within the mailing lists used to distribute the survey and, thus, do not know the total number of unique individuals reached across all lists, it is not possible to compute a response rate. The population of SMEs working on NASA-related topics with an interest in outreach is difficult to estimate. To take one figure, the SciAct itself claims to have engaged 963 scientists as of 2024 ([Learn - NASA Science, n.d.](#)). Another point of reference is 3207: the number of United States-based members of the American Astronomical Society ([Ivie & Pold, 2022](#)). In any event, the roughly 200 responses to our survey are certainly a minority within the population of interest; thus, some concern about selection bias is warranted. This is considered in the discussion section.

The first part of the survey asked respondents to report their satisfaction with their current

outreach opportunities and experiences, barriers faced in doing outreach, and what would support them in doing more outreach. The following section asked respondents to share the professional development opportunities they had participated in related to education and outreach in the past, and what kind of training they were willing to take part in in the future. This included not only format and structure, but also topics they were interested in learning more about.

The next section of the survey asked questions about SMEs' motivations and interests in doing outreach. Questions were asked about the most important personal reasons for taking part in public engagement activities, and respondents were asked to rate each reason on a scale from "1 - very low importance" to "7 - very high importance." These items were taken, unmodified, from the Portal to the Public evaluation ([Storksdieck et al., 2017](#)), which in turn builds upon prior research studying scientists' motivation to engage in outreach ([Besley et al., 2015](#); [Dudo & Besley, 2016](#)).

The final section of the survey consisted of demographic questions. These included asking about respondents' science disciplinary background, training and career stage, institution type, gender, race or ethnicity, and the option to self-identify as a member of an underserved group. The disciplinary background question used the NASA SMD Divisions (astrophysics, biological & physical science, Earth science, heliophysics, planetary science), in addition to astrobiology.

Respondents were asked to share their experiences with outreach, including the types of activities they had engaged in. Individuals who self-reported as graduate students were also asked about the topics they would like to be trained on to support their current or future work.

After the data were collected and organised, they were analysed primarily using descriptive statistics. Respondents' responses to motivation and interest questions were averaged and then compared to responses from prior studies.

3. Results

In several cases, we found that a brief discussion of the implications or context of our findings greatly aided understanding. Thus, we have chosen to include those in the Results section.

3.1. Respondent Demographics Our responses come predominantly from planetary scientists (48%), with Earth science (25%) and astrophysics (17%) also well-represented. Astrobiology, heliophysics, and biological & physical sciences each represent less than five per cent of the 203 responses to this question (see [Figure 1A](#)). Responses were fairly evenly distributed across career stages, with mid-career (6–19 years post-degree) and senior professionals (20+ years) each representing 32% of respondents, early-career (<6 years) representing 20% of respondents, and graduate students representing the remaining 15% ([Figure 1B](#)). Leaving aside graduate students, all of whom reported being enrolled at large research universities,

Figure 1 Summary of the participants' professional demographics. (A) Responses were evenly distributed across career stages. (B) Although close to half of respondents were from the planetary sciences, we received responses from across NASA science divisions. (C) Most respondents identified as scientists, with about 10% each identified as engineers or support staff. (D) Similar numbers of respondents work at government agencies, research universities, other colleges and universities, and in private research settings.

respondents reported working across a broad spectrum of organisations with ties to space science and engineering (Figure 1C). The most common were governmental agencies (29%), followed by large research universities (26%), other colleges and universities (21%), and private industry or private research institutes (15%). Finally, among the 173 non-graduate student responses, 82% consider their role to be that of a scientist with a PhD or Master's degree, 8% as engineers, and 11% as support staff (Figure 1D).

Respondents were invited to self-identify as a member of any underserved group. This category was left to the respondent's discretion, and 68% (199) of respondents chose to do so (Figure 2A). Only 35 respondents chose to describe these identities. These included identifying as a racial and ethnic minority in the U.S., having a marginalised gender identity and/or a sexual orientation, as well as those who identify as disabled (including learning disabilities, chronic disabilities, and other unspecified disabilities). Of the 202 responses to the gender identity question, 50% identified as female, 47% as male, 2% as non-binary, and 1% did not disclose (Figure 2B). Of the 201 responses to the race/ethnicity, the vast majority identified as White/European (77%). The next largest category was those identifying as two or more categories

Figure 2 Summary of the participants' personal demographics. (A) Roughly a third of respondents self-identified as being part of a group that is underserved in the sciences. (B) Respondents were nearly equally split between men and women, with only small percentage identifying as non-binary. (C) Respondents were overwhelmingly likely to be White/European.

(7%). This was followed by Latinx¹ (4%), Southern Asian (3%), Eastern Asian (2%), and Black or African American (2%) (Figure 2C). These demographics differ substantially from the overall U.S. population. Although we lack exact figures for the gender, racial, and ethnic makeup of NASA SMEs, a 2021 survey of U.S. members of the American Astronomical Society provides one estimate (Ivie & Pold, 2022). Those results were very similar to ours with respect to race and ethnicity, with 81% of respondents identifying as White, 10% as Asian or Asian American, 6% as Hispanic or Latino, and 2% as Black or African American. Ivie & Pold's 2022 survey found a considerably higher proportion of men (66% of the total population), although a breakdown by age shows that the group of younger members of the community (born in 1988 or later) was near gender parity.

Figure 3 Respondents' satisfaction with the amount and types of outreach opportunities available to them. (A) Just over half of the respondents wish they could do more outreach and nearly all of the remainder are satisfied with the current amount. (B) Roughly half of the respondents are somewhat or extremely satisfied with the types of outreach opportunities available to them, while about a quarter are dissatisfied to some extent.

3.2. History of and satisfaction with doing outreach Respondents were generally quite experienced in conducting outreach, with only 2% of the 201 valid responses to this question saying they had no previous experience and 18% reporting that they had done “one or a few events.” The remainder indicated that they regularly did at least one event per year (42%), at least one event per month (26%), or as someone who was formerly active but not currently engaging in outreach (12%). Individuals with prior outreach experience (n = 197) were asked about the range of types of outreach they had engaged in, given a list of broad categories and allowed to select as many as applied. Of these, by far the most common was Lectures or Discussions, with which 92% had experience. Hands-on activities (64%), Demonstrations (i.e., showing materials or a phenomenon without an opportunity for hands-on interaction; 57%), and Tours (56%) were also common, followed by citizen science (27%) as the least common of the provided choices. Only two people selected “none of the above,” which indicates that these categories provided good coverage of typical outreach performed by this community. The number of different types selected was well-distributed. Sixteen per cent had experience in only one type, 20% in two, 25% in three, 28% in four, and 11% selected all five categories.

Against that background, one of our main questions of interest was whether these scientists and engineers were satisfied with the amount of outreach they were currently doing ([Figure 3A](#)). Of this population, almost no one (1%, or three individuals) expressed a desire to do less outreach. By a small margin, the largest group (54%) wished to increase their outreach efforts, while 45% were satisfied with the current amount. Examining the results by career stage of the respondent, we observe the largest difference among graduate students, with 81% indicating a desire to do more outreach. Early career professionals somewhat mirror this trend, with 61% also wanting more outreach opportunities. Just under half of middle and late career respondents wanted more outreach opportunities. These results differed slightly when the amount of outreach the respondent is already doing is accounted for. Among those who had done only a few events, 75% wished to do more, while among those already doing at least one event per month, only 37% wished to do more outreach. The latter figure is still a considerable portion of the population, and notably, none of these individuals wished to do less outreach.

Turning to the types of outreach projects that respondents saw as available to them, respondents most commonly reported being somewhat satisfied with their options (39%; [Figure 3B](#)). The neutral response (27%) and somewhat dissatisfied (19%) were the next most common, pulling the central tendency of these responses to the middle of the available scale (mean = 3.4 on a 1–5 scale). Unlike the previous question, there was very little difference in responses by career stage.

3.3. Motivations for doing outreach Another important goal of our study is to understand the motivations of NASA scientists and engineers for engaging in outreach and their desired outcomes from their outreach work. This has both direct and indirect implications for how individuals from this community can be best recruited, supported, and retained by projects

aiming to expand the reach of NASA's education and outreach efforts. These results can also be compared to similar data collected in other domains and contexts to understand how, if at all, the motivations of scientists affiliated with NASA differ from those of scientists in other fields of study.

Looking first at respondents' personal reasons for taking part in public outreach and engagement ([Table 1](#)), the most strongly endorsed statements are very pro-social, including a desire to increase public knowledge and excitement about science (mean = 6.5/7) and to fulfill a sense of duty or give back to their community (mean = 6.0). The least strongly endorsed statements further support this largely selfless motivation, with fulfilling criteria for promotion (mean = 2.9), fulfilling expectations of the institution or funders (mean = 3.1), and increasing the odds of obtaining funding (mean = 3.0) all at the low end of the list. That is not to say the respondents get nothing out of their outreach work. Most also agree that outreach improves the impact of research (mean = 5.3) and most find it personally enjoyable (mean = 5.3) and intellectually gratifying (mean = 5.0).

Respondents' priorities when they do engage in outreach fall in a narrow range near the upper end of the scale ([Table 2](#)). The most universally endorsed was getting people excited about science (mean = 6.6/7). This was followed by a grouping between 6.0 and 6.2, which included making science relevant to the public, promoting a culture that values science, and encouraging people, in general, and girls and minorities in particular, to pursue careers in science. Note that the wording of the response item about girls and minorities was attempting to operationalise NSF's broadening participation goal. Less strongly endorsed, although still above the midpoint on the scale, were ensuring that scientific findings are part of the public debate (mean = 5.3) and hearing from the public about their views on scientific issues (mean = 5.0).

As described in the Methods section, the first two groups of survey questions ([Tables 1](#) and [2](#)) were also administered in identical form as part of the PoP evaluation ([Storksdieck et al., 2017](#)). Respondents in this earlier study had completed a structured training programme related to public outreach and engagement and would, therefore, be expected to hold relatively positive attitudes toward this work. Looking at the PoP data alongside the results from our survey, the responses are almost identical. The only notable exceptions are that our sample reports being less motivated by improvements to professional networks, by the opportunity to improve their own teaching, or by the hope of increasing their chances of obtaining research funding. One possible explanation for these differences is the much greater proportion of respondents in our study who work at non-teaching institutions. Limiting the population to only respondents from colleges and universities raises the average response for the "research funding" item to 3.5, but it has only a small impact on the "improve teaching" item, bringing this average to 4.5, which is still far below the 5.6 average of the PoP sample. The other possibility is that these differences stem from the specific structures and priorities of the PoP programme itself.

Table 1 Most important personal reasons for taking part in public engagement

Item	Mean (SD), This Study ^{1,2}	Mean, Portal to the Public ^{1,3}
Increase public knowledge and excitement about science	6.47 (0.94)	6.6
Fulfill a sense of duty (e.g., give back to my community)	6.01 (1.20)	6.0
Personal enjoyment	5.31 (1.42)	5.4
Improve the impact of research	5.27 (1.64)	5.4
Intellectual gratification	4.96 (1.55)	5.2
Involve the public in my research	4.38 (1.78)	4.6
Improve the impact of my teaching	4.38 (1.84)	5.6
Improve professional networks	4.04 (1.64)	4.7
Fulfill expectations of my institution, my funder, and/or my field/discipline	3.11 (1.73)	3.2
Increase the odds of obtaining research funding	3.04 (1.84)	3.7
Fulfill criterion for promotion, tenure or general job performance assessment	2.86 (1.72)	2.9

¹All responses on 1-7 point scale

²N = 208-212

³N = 287-290

Table 2 Priorities for public engagement

Item	Mean (SD), This Study ^{1,2}	Mean, Portal to the Public ^{1,3}
Getting people excited about science	6.55 (0.81)	6.6
Encouraging girls and minorities to pursue science as a career	6.23 (1.12)	6.1
Ensuring that people are informed about scientific issues	6.14 (1.12)	6.2
Describing scientific findings in ways that make them relevant to people	6.11 (1.04)	6.3
Ensuring that our culture values sciences	6.07 (1.15)	6.2
Encouraging more children and young adults to pursue science as a career	6.07 (1.20)	6.2
Getting people to appreciate the role of science in their daily lives	6.00 (1.22)	6.2
Correcting scientific misinformation	5.68 (1.41)	5.8
Helping people use science to make better decisions	5.64 (1.38)	5.8
Demonstrating that science advances society's wellbeing	5.47 (1.43)	5.8
Demonstrating that scientists share the values of their community	5.46 (1.50)	5.6
Ensuring that scientists' findings are part of the public debate	5.32 (1.51)	5.4
Hearing what others think about scientific issues	4.99 (1.47)	5.2

¹All responses on 1-7 point scale

²N = 208-211

³N = 285-286

3.4. Factors influencing whether an outreach project is appealing Another set of questions asked respondents to think about what makes a specific outreach project appealing to them. Choices included the types of audiences that might be reached, the time and effort required, and the format or nature of the outreach itself (Table 3).

Table 3 Factors that make an outreach project appealing

Item	Mean (SD), This Study ^{1,2}
Clear expectations for time commitment and requirements	5.87 (1.25)
Partner/organization makes it easy to find opportunities for participating in outreach	5.50 (1.38)
There are no costs to me	5.37 (1.72)
Set-up and support is provided	5.15 (1.36)
Flexibility for creative engagement	4.92 (1.32)
Local or regional focus/reach	4.76 (1.49)
Opportunities to make deep connections to communities	4.63 (1.39)
Fixed time commitment (i.e., one time events)	4.60 (1.57)
Having small enough groups to foster deeper learning and/or personal connections	4.39 (1.31)
National focus/reach	4.31 (1.55)
On-going involvement (i.e., repeated events or long-term projects)	4.06 (1.46)
International focus/reach	4.03 (1.73)
Having large audiences to engage with	3.70 (1.37)
External recognition is likely	3.54 (1.84)
Compensation is provided	3.38 (1.98)

¹All responses on 1-7 point scale

²N = 195-198

An outreach project will be more appealing if the organisers provide clear expectations, and this was the most positively endorsed item among our respondents (mean = 5.9/7). Similarly, respondents valued partners who made it easy to find outreach opportunities (mean = 5.5) and preferred opportunities where set-up and support are provided (mean = 5.2). Although opportunities without costs to the scientist were appreciated (mean = 5.4), actual compensation was the least endorsed of all the items in this section (mean = 3.4). Nor was external recognition very important (mean = 3.5). Finally, we asked a range of questions about the preferred size, frequency, and whether the programme primarily reached local or non-local audiences. From these, there was a general preference for smaller projects that might lead to deeper connections locally as opposed to projects that would reach large national or international audiences. That said, all of the items had average responses above average (4.0).

Looking at the type or format of outreach (Table 4), our respondents had a notable preference for in-person activities (mean = 6.0) over synchronous online ones (mean = 4.7) or asynchronous or no direct engagement, such as making videos (mean = 3.8). Engaging through social media was slightly less appealing than making videos, whether through the scientist’s own accounts (mean = 3.4) or through an organised event (mean = 3.8). Modality aside, lectures, classroom visits, and public events were each viewed positively (means just above 5). Many of the indirect or supporting forms of outreach work, such as editing or reviewing science content in educational materials or training educators, were less appealing (means around 4).

Table 4 Most appealing types of outreach

Item	Mean (SD), This Study ^{1,2}
In-person outreach/activities	6.01 (1.25)
Participating in public science festivals	5.38 (1.36)
Making classroom/camp visits	5.37 (1.34)
Participating in school science nights	5.20 (1.53)
Giving lectures	5.05 (1.48)
Translating science content into everyday language	4.97 (1.65)
Synchronous online outreach/activities (e.g. Zoom, Youtube, Facebook live etc)	4.72 (1.64)
Policy-related activities such as discussing research with decision-makers	4.65 (1.87)
Training teachers through workshops	4.55 (1.77)
Citizen science activities, crowd-sourcing, or community science	4.37 (1.75)
Reviewing science content in activities/websites/lessons	4.16 (1.68)
Training education and outreach professionals/volunteers	4.05 (1.75)
Editing science content in activities/websites/lessons	4.05 (1.71)
Making videos for outreach	3.83 (1.81)
Social media outreach/activities (e.g., using Twitch, Discord, Facebook, etc) as part of organized events	3.75 (1.99)
Social media outreach/activities (e.g., using Twitch, Discord, Facebook, etc) on your own personal social media accounts	3.41 (2.03)

¹All responses on 1-7 point scale

²N = 195-199

3.5. What specific barriers do these scientists face regarding outreach?

Figure 4 (A) Respondents' reported barriers to outreach participation and (B) incentives for outreach participation.

When asked about the barriers and challenges to engaging in more outreach (Figure 4A), the overriding obstacle among the 230 responses to this question was a lack of time due to other commitments (79%). Two other common responses were a lack of knowledge about opportunities (41%) and a lack of connections to communities to do outreach (37%). A relatively small number of respondents (19%) listed a lack of training or knowledge (17%) as reasons for not being able to prepare and conduct outreach activities.

When asked about incentives and support that might encourage them to participate in more outreach activities (Figure 4B), the most popular option was grants or financial support (59%), followed by salary support (49%) and travel funding (40%). More support from partners, either in the form of invitations to specific outreach opportunities (44%) or venues/platforms that would enable outreach (38%), was also appealing to some respondents. Consistent with the responses to the barrier questions, outreach training was not seen as a key need by our respondents, with each form of training receiving support from less than 30% of this population.

3.6. What types of training are these scientists interested in regarding outreach? Although some of our results thus far indicate that few NASA scientists and engineers see outreach training as the key obstacle to their work in that domain, prior research argues that outreach training is valuable (Besley et al., 2015; Illingworth & Roop, 2015; Stylinski et al., 2018; Copple et al., 2020; Lewenstein & Baram-Tsabari, 2022). Asked about previous training in outreach (Table 5), 70% of our 214 valid responses indicated that they had no such training. Among those who reported having prior training, 75% felt that the training had helped them professionally.

Table 5 Previous outreach-related training

Training	Percent of Respondents ¹
None	70.1
Other	15.4
AGU Voices for Science	8.4
AAAS Communicating Science Workshops	5.1
AAS Astronomy Ambassador Program	3.7
STEM Ambassador Program	2.3
COMPASS (Communication Partnership for Science and the Sea)	0.5
Portal to the Public (POPNet)	0.5
Advancing Research Impact in Society (ARIS)	0.0
Communicating Ocean Sciences to the Informal Audience (COSIA)	0.0

¹N = 214

Sources of training were almost all through professional societies and conferences (e.g., the American Geophysical Union, Lunar and Planetary Science Conference) or initiatives aimed at improving science communication (notably, the Alan Alda Center for Communicating Science).

To inform groups that wish to provide outreach training to scientists, we asked about the format and topics of such training that would be appealing to our respondents ([Figure 5A](#)). A hybrid in-person/virtual format was the most popular at 66%, but only by a small margin over the other choices, including fully virtual (63%), fully in-person (61%), and asynchronous or on-demand virtual training (56%). Respondents had a stronger consensus on preferred training duration ([Figure 5B](#)), with 73% preferring a single 1–2 hour training session and 45% preferring a single 2–4 hour training session. Other longer options were of interest to smaller proportions. Interestingly, almost half (47%) of the respondents to this question were interested in receiving training in the form of a review and feedback on their own outreach work.

Regarding the topics of outreach training ([Figure 5C](#)), the three most popular options all relate to learning about how to make outreach accessible to be effective for diverse participants. This included learning about ways to engage with different underserved audiences (65%), learning to communicate to specific age groups (55%), and the general topic of accessibility in outreach (51%). Much less interesting to this group were training sessions on topics such as working with international audiences (21%), fundraising and development work for outreach (23%), writing activity and lesson plans (26%), and engaging in policy work (28%).

Figure 5 Respondents’ preferences regarding training modality (A), duration (B), and topics (C).

4. Discussion

4.1. Key takeaways from our results The most consistent and notable pattern in our results is the enthusiasm and dedication to public outreach reported by our respondents. The typical respondent engages in at least one outreach event per year, and a quarter do so monthly. And just over half of all respondents wished to engage in more outreach than they currently perform. This point was even more true for graduate students and early-career scientists. Moreover, our respondents overwhelmingly report that they engage in outreach due to a sense that it is the duty of scientists to give back to their communities and to increase public knowledge and excitement about science. Respondents also felt strongly that outreach was an important opportunity to improve the diversity of the scientific profession. They reported that outreach was a way to excite young people about careers in science, but particularly girls and people from minority groups. Looking at previous data on these questions ([Besley et al., 2015](#); [Dudo & Besley, 2016](#); [Stylinski et al., 2018](#)), we find that the motivations for engaging in outreach and the desired objectives from outreach of our respondents are quite similar to those of scientists from other disciplines. This provides further support for the idea that these attitudes are common among scientists across various disciplines.

It should also be noted that, although our respondents indicate that compensation is a minor motivation for engaging in education and outreach, when asked about barriers and incentives, they report that salary and travel support are among the most significant. In other words, selfless motivations and a belief in the societal importance of outreach cannot entirely eliminate the practical constraints of finite time and limited financial and other resources. Moreover, graduate students and early-career scientists were substantially more likely to say that financial support was an important incentive for outreach participation, so this may be a particularly important barrier to overcome if projects hope to include students and early-career scientists in their outreach work.

4.2. Recommendations for groups or organizations who work with SMEs on outreach The results of this study have been useful for our work and have been used to create a list of recommendations to share more broadly with groups and/or organisations that work with, or plan to engage, SMEs in outreach related to Earth and Space Science, and potentially other content areas. Providing support and bridging partnerships are important components for successfully recruiting and maintaining scientists in outreach efforts. This support should ideally make it easy for SMEs to participate in outreach activities, such as, connecting them to communities and audiences interested in engaging with a SME, providing them resources for their outreach, and when needed, providing training, to help them make the most out of their outreach experiences. A lack of time was the top-reported challenge to engaging in outreach. Providing the resources and connections will ensure that SMEs can focus on the outreach and not spend a lot of time preparing materials that already exist. This strategy enables support organisations to utilise their expertise to effectively support the outreach work of SMEs.

The opportunity to engage directly with people was a priority. A large percentage of the SMEs

surveyed in this work valued conducting in-person activities with smaller groups instead of large-scale outreach. Similarly, outreach involving social media was the least popular of all the categories surveyed. When considering how to reach geographically underserved audiences, such as rural communities, being creative about synchronous virtual outreach may be worth exploring, as it could maintain the personal connections that SMEs value in their outreach efforts while expanding the pool of SMEs who could potentially work with those communities.

When considering the provision of training to SMEs, relatively few respondents (30%) reported having formal training in outreach. Despite this, few (<20%) felt that their lack of training was a barrier to doing outreach. Most (>70%) would consider attending outreach training, with a large percentage of respondents reporting interest in training around working with diverse learners and how to engage audiences of different age groups. In particular, SMEs are looking for “bite-sized” training in the form of short (1-2 hours) single sessions. Although not included in the survey, one strategy that groups coordinating education and outreach programmes might consider is the “just in time” training model, in which these short trainings are tailored to and offered in concert with specific outreach activities. Similarly, SMEs could be offered rapid, personalised feedback on outreach materials or ideas for outreach activities. This aligns with one of the more popular options on our survey (see [Figure 5B](#)).

4.3. Limitations As with most survey research, the most important limitation to this work is the size and non-representativeness of the study population. We do not claim that our findings represent the average NASA scientist or engineer. First, our focus on NASA brings a substantial bias towards U.S. residents and educational settings. Second, by choosing to take the time to respond to our survey, these respondents are very likely to have more positive attitudes toward outreach or more experience with outreach than the average person among their professional peers. Therefore, our results likely reflect the attitudes and experiences of the subset of NASA scientists and engineers who already engage in outreach. However, we cannot say with confidence that our results reflect the views of the many scientists and engineers who do not currently participate in outreach. This may be a particularly salient limitation for projects looking to draw new people into scientific outreach. As one point of reference for our selection bias, the 2021 AAS member survey reported that 44% of those working at a university or four-year college and 38% of those in all other sectors engage regularly in some education and public outreach. 80% of our sample were currently or formerly active at that level.

Second, although we did collect and report participant demographics, we avoided substantial analysis of trends in the various outreach attitudes and behaviours across demographic groups. There are likely meaningful differences on these attitudes and behaviours between different subpopulations, however, as our study lacked a strong theoretical basis for exploring those relationships and we did not explicitly include potential differences in attitudes and behaviours by specific demographic characteristics in our research questions, any analysis

we might conduct around select demographics would risk reporting spurious associations. We hope future researchers will take our results as a starting point for designing future studies.

Finally, it must be noted that the survey was distributed in mid-2021; thus, our respondents had had more than a year of virtual meetings, conferences, or classes. This may have impacted some of their preferences regarding in-person versus virtual training and outreach. Beyond the timing of our data collection, attitudes toward online/virtual events are likely to change more quickly than the other topics surveyed as new technologies are developed and improved.

5. Conclusions

Understanding the motivations, needs, and challenges of NASA's SMEs has informed how we recruit SMEs for outreach work, the types of training we provide, and how we incentivise SMEs to engage in outreach projects. For example, Planetary ReaCH project utilised the results to inform the types of topics covered in its workshops for planetary scientists across the US, thereby supporting their work with diverse youth and families. NASA SMD Community of Practice for Education project has multiple strategies that follow directly from the results shown in [Figure 4](#), including efforts to match SMEs with groups that run outreach events and efforts to provide small grants to support outreach work. We also shared these results within the NASA SciAct program.

We are continually refining our approach to this work as we gather feedback in specific projects; however, this work laid the groundwork for understanding where to start in our efforts. Our hope is that by sharing this information broadly, others can learn from our efforts and share their own findings.

In addition to the implications for practice among those supporting outreach work, our study also suggests several directions for future research. Our literature review highlighted a gap in views about learning between scientists and educational best practices, with scientists being more likely to hold transmissionist views. This topic was not included in our survey, but it would be an important area for subsequent survey work to explore.

Responses from our survey indicate that many scientists and engineers are interested in learning how to more effectively engage with young people and individuals from underrepresented groups in these fields. The goal of bringing greater diversity to science and engineering is widely shared, including being a common feature in the NASA scientific divisions' Decadal Surveys ([Most Recent Decadal Surveys - NASA Science, n.d.](#)). As it relates to the question of how to meet this reported need for training, future work could explore whether such training programs materially change how trainees engage with these audiences in outreach and whether those changes in behaviour or approach result in more positive outcomes for audiences.

Acknowledgements The authors would like to thank the NASA Science Activation programme collectively for their contributions to this work. We would also like to thank the following Science Activation teams and individual contributors for suggesting survey questions and topics to include and/or for help in distributing the survey: Cosmic Storytelling with NASA Data, Eclipse Soundscapes, GLOBE Mission Earth, Infiniscope, NASA Astromaterials, NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative, NASA Heliophysics Education Activation Team, NASA's Universe of Learning, Planetary ReaCH, Smoky Mountains STEM Collaborative, STEM Ecosystems, STEM Enhancement in Earth Science. In addition, the authors acknowledge funding from NASA under the following awards: 80NSSC21M0006 (NASA SMD Community of Practice for Education, M. Wadhwa), NNX16AE28A (NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative, T. Schwerin), 80NSSC22K1356 (NASA HEAT, M. Kirk). Finally, we thank the anonymous reviewers from CAPjournal and the Astronomy Education Journal for their helpful comments and suggestions.

Notes

1. Latinx is one of several gender-neutral terms used in the United States for individuals of Latin American ethnicities. Other similar words are Latino/Latina or Latine.

References

- American Association for the Advancement of Science. (2016). *Theory of change for public engagement with science*. https://www.aaas.org/sites/default/files/content_files/2016-09-15_PES_Theory-of-Change-for-Public-Engagement-with-Science_Final.pdf
- Andrews, E., Weaver, A., Hanley, D., Shamatha, J., & Melton, G. (2005). Scientists and Public Outreach: Participation, Motivations, and Impediments. *Journal of Geoscience Education*, 53(3), 281–293. <https://doi.org/10.5408/1089-9995-53.3.281>
- Barthel, C. F. (2020). *Exploring the Relationship Between Scientists' Perspectives on Learning and Engagement in Outreach*.
- Besley, J. C., Dudo, A., & Storksdieck, M. (2015). Scientists' views about communication training. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 52(2), 199–220. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21186>
- Besley, J. C., Newman, T. P., Dudo, A., & Tiffany, L. A. (2020). Exploring scholars' public engagement goals in Canada and the United States. *Public Understanding of Science*, 29(8), 855–867. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520950671>
- Bowring, S. A. (2013). Perceptions of time matter: The importance of geoscience outreach. In *Geoscience Research and Outreach: Schools and Public Engagement* (pp. 11–15). Springer.

Bush, J. M., Jung, H., Connell, J. P., & Freeberg, T. M. (2018). Duty now for the future: A call for public outreach by animal behaviour researchers. *Animal Behaviour*, 139, 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2018.03.013>

Copple, J., Bennett, N., Dudo, A., Moon, W.-K., Newman, T. P., Besley, J., Leavey, N., Lindenfeld, L., & Volpe, C. (2020). Contribution of Training to Scientists' Public Engagement Intentions: A Test of Indirect Relationships Using Parallel Multiple Mediation. *Science Communication*, 42(4), 508–537. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547020943594>

Dang, L., & Russo, P. (2015). *How Astronomers View Education and Public Outreach: An Exploratory Study*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1507.08552>

Dudo, A., & Besley, J. C. (2016). Scientists' Prioritization of Communication Objectives for Public Engagement. *PLOS ONE*, 11(2), e0148867. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148867>

Ecklund, E. H., James, S. A., & Lincoln, A. E. (2012). How Academic Biologists and Physicists View Science Outreach. *PLoS ONE*, 7(5), e36240. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0036240>

Illingworth, S., & Roop, H. (2015). Developing Key Skills as a Science Communicator: Case Studies of Two Scientist-Led Outreach Programmes. *Geosciences*, 5(1), 2–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences5010002>

Ivie, R., & Pold, J. (2022). *Workforce Survey of 2021 US AAS Members Summary Results*. American Institute of Physics. https://aas.org/sites/default/files/2022-11/2021_AAS-Members-Workforce-Survey.pdf

Johnson, D. R., Ecklund, E. H., & Lincoln, A. E. (2014). Narratives of Science Outreach in Elite Contexts of Academic Science. *Science Communication*, 36(1), 81–105. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547013499142>

Kaminski, A. P. (2021). *Space Science and Public Engagement: 21st Century Perspectives and Opportunities*. Elsevier Science. <https://books.google.com/books?id=aAoPEAAAQBAJ>

Learn—NASA Science. (n.d.). Retrieved May 8, 2024, from <https://science.nasa.gov/learn/>

Lewenstein, B. V., & Baram-Tsabari, A. (2022). How should we organize science communication trainings to achieve competencies? *International Journal of Science Education, Part B*, 12(4), 289–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21548455.2022.2136985>

Mackay, S. M., Tan, E. W., & Warren, D. S. (2020). Developing a new generation of scientist communicators through effective public outreach. *Communications Chemistry*, 3(1), 76. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42004-020-0315-0>

Most Recent Decadal Surveys—NASA Science. (n.d.). Retrieved May 8, 2024, from <https://science.nasa.gov/about-us/science-strategy/decadal-surveys/>

NASA Strategic Plan. (n.d.). Retrieved May 8, 2024, from <https://www.nasa.gov/ocfo/strategic-plan/>

National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine. (2018). *Thriving on Our Changing Planet: A Decadal Strategy for Earth Observation from Space*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24938>

National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine. (2019). *NASA's Science Activation Program* (M. A. Honey, K. A. Dibner, & T. E. E. Taylor, Eds.). National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25569>

National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine. (2023a). *Origins, Worlds, and Life: A Decadal Strategy for Planetary Science and Astrobiology 2023-2032*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26522>

National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine. (2023b). *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26141>

National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine. (2023c). *Thriving in Space: Ensuring the Future of Biological and Physical Sciences Research: A Decadal Survey for 2023-2032*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26750>

National Research Council. (2013). *Solar and Space Physics: A Science for a Technological Society*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/13060>

Poliakoff, E., & Webb, T. L. (2007). What Factors Predict Scientists' Intentions to Participate in Public Engagement of Science Activities? *Science Communication*, 29(2), 242–263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547007308009>

Rose, K. M., Markowitz, E. M., & Brossard, D. (2020). Scientists' incentives and attitudes toward public communication. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(3), 1274–1276. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1916740117>

Scheufele, D. A., Krause, N. M., Freiling, I., & Brossard, D. (2021). What we know about effective public engagement on CRISPR and beyond. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(22), e2004835117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2004835117>

Selvakumar, M., & Storksdieck, M. (2013). Portal to the Public: Museum Educators Collaborating with Scientists to Engage Museum Visitors with Current Science. *Curator: The Museum Journal*, 56(1), 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cura.12007>

Storksdieck, M., Stylinski, C., & Bailey, D. (2016). Typology for public engagement with science: A conceptual framework for public engagement involving scientists. *Center for Research on Lifelong STEM Learning*.

Storksdieck, M., Stylinski, C., & Canzoneri, N. (2017). *The Impact of Portal to the Public: Creating an Infrastructure for Engaging Scientists in Informal Science Education: Summative Evaluation*.

Stylinski, C., Storksdieck, M., Canzoneri, N., Klein, E., & Johnson, A. (2018). Impacts of a comprehensive public engagement training and support program on scientists' outreach attitudes and practices. *International Journal of Science Education, Part B*, 8(4), 340–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21548455.2018.1506188>

Varner, J. (2014). Scientific Outreach: Toward Effective Public Engagement with Biological Science. *BioScience*, 64(4), 333–340. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biu021>

Woitowich, N. C., Hunt, G. C., Muhammad, L. N., & Garbarino, J. (2022). Assessing motivations and barriers to science outreach within academic science research settings: A mixed-methods survey. *Frontiers in Communication*, 7, 907762. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2022.907762>

Appendix

Appendix A: Complete Survey

Start of Block Inclusion criterion

Do you consider yourself to be a scientist or engineer working on NASA-related topics? This is intended to be inclusive of graduate students.

- Yes
- I'm not sure
- No

Skip to the end of the survey if respondents answer "No" to this question.

End of Block: Inclusion criterion

Start of Block Barriers to Education and Outreach

This survey relates to participation in outreach activities. By this, we mean a broad array of activities, such as: giving a talk to a school or classroom, advising on a visualization tool for museums or planetarium show, or giving a NASA hyperwall talk at a conference.

The survey is not intended to include formal education activities such as serving as the instructor of record for a course. If you have a teaching appointment, please limit your responses to education and outreach activities outside of your formal role.

Are you satisfied with the amount of outreach you typically engage in?

- Yes
- No, I would like to do MORE outreach
- No, I would like to do LESS outreach

How satisfied with the types of outreach projects that are available for you to participate in?

- Extremely dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

What are main barriers and/or challenges for you to do (more) outreach activities? (select all the apply).

- Lack of time due to job/school commitments
- Difficulty scheduling around job/school commitments
- Lack of time due to personal commitments

-
- Lack of connections to communities to do outreach
 - Lack of opportunities to do outreach
 - Lack of knowledge about opportunities
 - Live too far away from places to conduct outreach
 - Lack of advisor/supervisor support to do outreach
 - Not allowed by advisor/employer, must be done on personal time
 - Lack of support/collaborators for successful events
 - Lack of readily usable activities and materials
 - Feel that I need more knowledge and skills to engage audiences
 - Lack of training or professional development/learning to prepare for outreach
 - Too much time is needed to prepare for events
 - Don't feel comfortable doing outreach
 - Lack of inspiring role models
 - Not enough support and encouragement from my peers
 - Not enough incentive to conduct outreach
 - Other (please describe)

What would allow or incentivize you to do more outreach? (select all that apply)

- Salary support
- Grant/financial support for outreach
- Childcare/family support
- More support from leadership (advisor/supervisor/employer)
- Travel funding
- External recognition to give to my leadership (e.g. outreach award, letter from partner)
- Readily made materials to use in outreach
- More invitations from partners to do outreach
- Easily accessible platforms or opportunities to conduct my outreach
- Outreach training at scientific conferences (e.g., AGU, AAS)
- Outreach training provided by reputable institutions outside of conferences (e.g., Portal to the Public, COMPASS, Astronomy Ambassadors, STEMAP)
- Mentorship or direct support from experts in outreach or experienced peers
- Other (please describe)

Please share anything else you would like us to know about the barriers you face in doing outreach.

End of Block Barriers to Education and Outreach

Start of Block Training

Which of the following professional development activities have you attended? (Check all that you have attended.)

- AAAS Communicating Science Workshops
- AAS Astronomy Ambassador Program
- Advancing Research Impact in Society (ARIS)
- AGU Voices for Science
- Communicating Ocean Sciences to the Informal Audience (COSIA)
- COMPASS (Communication Partnership for Science and the Sea)
- Portal to the Public (POPNet)
- STEM Ambassador Program
- Other
- None

If applicable, do you feel the professional development you received for engaging in outreach helped you professionally?

- Yes
- No

Please briefly describe how this training was useful to you.

What kind of training are you willing to participate in related to outreach? (choose all that apply)

- In-person training
- Synchronous virtual training
- Asynchronous/On-demand virtual training
- Hybrid (some in person and some virtual)

Which structures and lengths of outreach training would you consider attending? (choose all that apply)

- A single 1–2 hour training
- A single 2–4 hour training
- Multiple half day trainings
- A single full day training
- Consecutive multi-day trainings
- A multi-day training over a period of time (weeks or months)
- Personal review and feedback on your participation in an outreach event (i.e. debriefing of your talk or receiving pointers on talking to different audiences)
- None

What topics are of interest to you for outreach training? (choose all that apply)

- Accessibility training for engagement (e.g. identifying and understanding diverse learners and ways to engage effectively) and making accessible presentations for differently-abled learners
- Learning about ways to effectively engage with different underserved audiences (e.g. urban, rural, racially and ethnically diverse)
- Learning to communicate to specific age groups (e.g., middle school, high school, etc.)
- Learning how to write activity/lesson plans
- Social media training
- Media/communications training
- Learning about effective ways to teach
- Learning about how people learn
- Learning and practicing activities to use in outreach
- Learning about fundraising/development for outreach work
- Learning how to work with international audiences
- Learning how to engage in policy work
- Learning how to assess audience learning and engagement during events
- Other (please describe)
- None of the above

Please share anything else you would like us to know about training.

End of Block Training

Start of Block Motivations and Interests to do Outreach

What do you see as your most important personal reasons for taking part in public engagement? The rating varies from "very low importance" (1) to "average importance" (4) to "very high importance" (7).

- Personal enjoyment
- Improve the impact of research
- Improve the impact of my teaching
- Increase the odds of obtaining research funding
- Intellectual gratification
- Fulfill a sense of duty (e.g., give back to my community)
- Improve professional networks
- Increase public knowledge and excitement about science
- Involve the public in my research
- Fulfill expectations of my institution, my funder, and/or my field/discipline

Fulfill criterion for promotion, tenure or general job performance assessment

How much are each of the objectives below a priority for you when you engage the public? The rating varies from "very low priority" (1) to "average priority" (4) to very high priority (7).

- Ensuring that people are informed about scientific issues
- Ensuring that scientists' findings are part of the public debate
- Getting people excited about science
- Getting people to appreciate the role of science in their daily lives
- Hearing what others think about scientific issues
- Demonstrating that science advances society's wellbeing
- Describing scientific findings in ways that make them relevant to people
- Correcting scientific misinformation
- Demonstrating that scientists share the values of their community
- Encouraging more children and young adults to pursue science as a career
- Encouraging girls and minorities to pursue science as a career
- Helping people use science to make better decisions
- Ensuring that our culture values sciences

Do you have any important motivations or objectives related to outreach that were not covered above? If so, please explain.

How important are each of the following factors in determining whether an outreach project is appealing to you? The rating varies from "very low importance" (1) to "average importance" (4) to "very high importance" (7).

- Clear expectations for time commitment and requirements
- Partner/organization makes it easy to find opportunities for participating in outreach
- Having large audiences to engage with
- Having small enough groups to foster deeper learning and/or personal connections
- Opportunities to make deep connections to communities
- Fixed time commitment (i.e., one time events)
- On-going involvement (i.e., repeated events or long-term projects)
- Local or regional focus/reach
- National focus/reach
- International focus/reach
- Flexibility for creative engagement
- Set-up and support is provided
- There are no costs to me
- Compensation is provided
- External recognition is likely

Outreach can take many forms. How appealing are each of the following types of projects to you? The rating varies from “very unappealing” (1) to “average” (4) to “very appealing” (7).

- In-person outreach/activities
- Synchronous online outreach/activities (e.g. Zoom, Youtube, Facebook live etc)
- Social media outreach/activities (e.g., using Twitch, Discord, Facebook, etc) on your own personal social media accounts
- Social media outreach/activities (e.g., using Twitch, Discord, Facebook, etc) as part of organized events
- Making videos for outreach
- Giving lectures
- Making classroom/camp visits
- Participating in school science nights
- Participating in public science festivals
- Reviewing science content in activities/websites/lessons
- Editing science content in activities/websites/lessons
- Training education and outreach professionals/volunteers
- Training teachers through workshops
- Translating science content into everyday language
- Policy-related activities such as discussing research with decision-makers
- Citizen science activities, crowd-sourcing, or community science

Do you have any important considerations when choosing an outreach project that were not covered above? If so, please explain.

End of Block Motivations and Interests to do Outreach

Start of Block Demographics

The following questions are optional. Please share whatever information you are comfortable with.

Do you have experience participating in outreach?

- Yes, I have done one or a few events
- Yes, I am active in outreach (e.g. at least one event a year)
- Yes, I am very active in outreach (e.g. at least one event a month, part of my job, etc)
- Yes, I was active in the past but not right now
- No, I have no experience but want to become involved

Which of the following basic type(s) of public outreach activities have you conducted so far? (Check all that apply.)

- Hands-on activity in which the audience directly manipulates objects

-
- Demonstration in which the audience observes but does not directly manipulate objects.
 - Tour (e.g., lab tour, nature walk, etc.)
 - Lecture or discussion with audience interaction
 - Citizen science (e.g., providing data sets, serving as a research advisor)
 - None of the above

Are you currently a graduate student?

- Yes
- No

If the respondent answers "Yes" to the question, Are you currently a graduate student?, display the following questions:

Which best describes your current academic status?

- Master's student
- Early PhD student (prior to qualifying exam)
- Advanced PhD student/candidate (post-qualifying exam)
- Other graduate student (please describe)

At which type of institution are you studying?

- Large research university (PhD granting in science or engineering)
- College or university (non-PhD granting in science or engineering)
- Other

If applicable, at which type of institutions do you work (choose all that apply)?

- The college/university where I am a graduate student
- Another college or university
- Museum/Planetarium (Public Outreach and Education Setting)
- Private Industry or Research Setting (e.g., PSI, LPI, STScl, Raytheon)
- Non Government Organization
- Other

If the respondent answers "No" to the question, Are you currently a graduate student?, display the following questions:

Which best describes your professional role?

- PhD level research scientist
- Faculty member in science
- Faculty member in engineering
- Master's level research scientist

-
- Engineer (PhD or Master's)
 - Engineer (Bachelor's level)
 - Graduate student in science
 - Graduate student in engineering
 - Science support staff
 - Technical support staff
 - Other (please specify)

Which of these experience levels best describes your current career stage?

- Early-career professional (current graduate student or less than six years post degree)
- Mid-career professional (six to 19 years post degree working in a science field)
- Senior professional (20 or more years working in a science field)

Which type of institution primarily employs you?

- Governmental Agency (e.g., NASA)
- Large Research University (PhD granting)
- College or University
- Community College
- Museum/Planetarium (Public Outreach and Education Setting)
- Private Industry or Research Setting (e.g., PSI, LPI, STScl, Raytheon)
- Non Government Organizations
- K-12 Formal Education System
- Self-employed
- Other

Which of the following NASA SMD divisions best aligns with your expertise?

- Astrobiology
- Astrophysics
- Biological and Physical Sciences
- Earth Science
- Heliophysics
- Planetary Science
- Other

Do you identify with any underserved groups?

- Yes
- No

If the respondent answers "Yes" to the question, *Do you identify with any underserved groups?*, display the following question:

If you feel comfortable, please describe.

How do you identify your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / Gender fluid
- Other
- Prefer not to say

How do you identify your race/ethnicity? (choose all that apply)

- White/European
- Black or African American
- Native American
- Eastern Asian
- Southern Asian
- Western Asian
- Hawaiian/Pacific Islander
- Latinx
- Mixed
- Other
- Prefer not to say

End of Block Demographics